

The Role of Applying the Quality Standards of University Education in Enhancing the Quality of Academic Performance in Jordanian Universities A Case Study of Zarqa University in Jordan

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Abstract

The study aimed to identify the role of the application of quality standards of university education in enhancing the quality of academic performance in Jordanian universities: a case study of Zarqa University. To achieve this purpose has been to build and develop a questionnaire included seven standards for the quality of university education, and the variable of academic performance, consisted of (45) items, were then test the sincerity of the tool and its reliability, was applied to the study sample of (116) teaching staff, chosen at random of the study population (253) teaching staff using a stratified random sample. The study findings a number of results, including:

1-There is statistically significant relationship (positive correlation) at the level ($\alpha = 0.05$), between each of the quality standards of university education and the academic performance quality.

2- There are no statistically significant differences at the level ($\alpha = 0.05$), between the means responses of the study sample about the applying degree of the educational quality standards, which indicates that the homogeneity of the study sample responses about the applying degree the standards from the point of view.

3- There are exist statistically significant differences at the level ($\alpha = 0.05$), between the means responses of the study sample about the applying degree of the quality standards of university education, attributed to (experience years in the university), in favor of the class (4-8) years.

4- There are no statistically significant differences at the level ($\alpha = 0.05$), between the means responses of the study sample about the applying degree of the quality standards of university education, attributed to (job title, qualification, and academic rank).

5- There are no statistically significant differences between the means responses of the study sample about the evaluation level of the quality of academic performance, attributed to (job title, qualification, academic rank, and experience years in the university).

Key words: Quality of Higher Education, the Quality of Academic Performance, Zarqa University, Jordan.

1-Introduction:

There is no doubt that the process of reform programs, policies and strategies of education in general has received considerable attention in most countries of the world, and in this regard has been given a comprehensive quality along much of this interest, as one of the pillars of productivity management model university modern in order to face the changes of local, regional and global order adaptation, and it has become the global community to consider the overall quality system and the educational administration as a basis for the development of peoples and progress, where we can say that the overall quality system is the real challenge that will face United in the coming decades (Ahmed,2003:27).

The renewal of programs and strategies of education through the adoption of TQM has taken echoed widespread in higher education, where he sees specialists in the field of management that the application of total quality management in universities is an integrated approach to system standards can be applied at all levels of the university and colleges to

provide for employees and teams the opportunity to satisfy the needs of students and the beneficiaries of higher education.

In light of the foregoing, the educational quality has not tad gift granted by governments, but the opportunity to invest and manufactured Nations peoples, and sacrifice for it time and effort, money and perseverance. And verify the educational quality through the existence of a clear policy for the system of total quality, and efficiency of the administrative organization of educational institutions, the academic in Jordanian universities, and activate the system, monitoring and evaluation to avoid falling into the errors, and provide training system effectively to teaching staff (Al-ithawi, and Al-samarrai, 2011: 6).

Because the current study concerned with assessing the role of quality standards of university education in enhancing the quality of academic performance case study of Zarqa University . Therefore behooves the modern Scholar Zarqa University for their betterment current:

Zarqa University was established in year (1994) by decision of the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research with a number (48) in the 1994, and considered this university one of the centers of cultural, scientific and intellectual in the governorate of Zarqa, Jordan, The University (13) faculty of science and humanity was faculties (pharmacy, engineering technology, science & information technology, nursing, medical science supporting, economics & administrative sciences, educational sciences, arts, law code, laws, arts & design, and journalism & the media), in addition to the presence of (5) science centers where, and the number of students University (6635) male and female students in graduate studies, in addition to (39) male and female students in post graduate studies.

2- Methodology:

2-1: Study Problem and its Questions:

Reflected in the detection problem of the study on the mechanisms by which applying the quality standards of university education in enhancing the quality of academic performance in Jordanian universities, and the trouble with the study of wonder the following:

- a – What is the degree of the application of educational quality standards in Zarqa University from the view point of the study sample?
- b - What is the level to assess the quality of academic performance in Zarqa University from the view point of the study sample?
- c – What is the nature of the relationship between each of the quality standards of university education and the quality of academic performance?
- d - Is there exist a different between the means responses of the study sample in applying the quality standards of university education at Zarqa University from the view point?
- e - Is there exist a different between the means responses of the study sample in applying the quality standards of university education, attributed to some personality variables (job title, qualification, academic rank, and experience years in the university)?
- f- Is there exist a different between the means responses of the study sample in the evaluation level of the academic performance quality, attributed to some personality variables (job title, qualification, academic rank, and experience years in the university)?

2-2: Study Importance:

Gaining importance in the study as it deals with a subject extremely sensitive is the quality of university education, which is reflected in a positive way to enhance the quality of academic performance in Jordanian universities. Also, according to this study provide a number of requirements for quality of university education, which can be used to enhance the quality of academic performance of faculty members

at the university on the one hand, on the other hand, benefit the designers of systems, the quality of university education by providing them with a list of standards to ensure quality of teaching, as well as benefit officials in higher education and through the entrances to identify a modern management represented by (the quality of university education) and provide standards to be applied in order to enhance the quality of academic performance in Jordanian universities.

2-3: Study Objectives:

The study aims to achieving the following objectives:

- a- To identify the concepts of quality of university education, and academic performance .
- b- To identify the applying degree the educational quality standards in Zarqa University from the view point of the study sample.
- c- To identify the evaluation level of the quality of academic performance in Zarqa University from the view point of the study sample.
- d- To identify the role of the applying of the educational quality standards in enhancing the quality of academic performance at Zarqa University.
- e - To identify the nature of the relationship between each one of the quality standards of university education and the quality of academic performance.
- f- To Measure the difference between means responses of the study sample about applying the educational quality standards in Zarqa university.
- g- To Measure the differences between means responses of the study sample about the applying degree of the quality standards of university education, attributed to some personality variables (job title, qualification, academic rank, and experience years in the university).
- h- To Measure the differences between means responses of the study sample about the evaluation level the quality of academic performance, attributed to some personality variables (job title, qualification, academic rank, and experience years in university).

2-4: Study Hypotheses:

To achieve the study objectives, it has been putting some statistical hypotheses as null (H_0), and as follows:

The first hypothesis:

H_{01} : There is no statistically significant relationship at the level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), between each one of the quality

standards of university education and the quality of academic performance.

The second hypothesis:

H₀₂: There are no statistically significant differences at the level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), between means responses of the study sample about applying the educational quality standards in Zarqa university from the view point.

The third hypothesis:

H₀₃: There are no statistically significant differences at the level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), between the means responses of the study sample about the applying degree of the educational quality standards, attributed to some personality variables (job title, qualification, academic rank, and experience years in the university).

The fourth hypothesis:

H₀₄: There are no statistically significant differences at the level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), between the means responses of the study sample about the evaluation level of the academic performance quality, attributed to some personality variables (job title, qualification, academic rank, and experience years in the university).

2-5: Study Terms:

a - Quality:

The Quality is defined by the National Committee for Quality Assurance and Accreditation Quality as "the degree to meet the requirements expected by the service user, or those agreed with him" (National Committee for Quality Assurance and Accreditation, 2004).

b - Education Quality:

Education Quality Good quality of education is defined as: "a translation of the needs and expectations of the student to the specific characteristics as a basis in their education and training so as to match the aspirations of students" (Al-rashid, 1995: 7).

c – The Performance:

Performance is defined as psoriatic Performance: "scale of what has been accomplished by the work of the institution or a team or a particular person" (Al-sadafy, 2004:8).

d - The Performance Quality:

Performance Quality is defined as: "to contribute the effective system of administrative and regulatory framework with all its elements in achieving efficient investment of available resources (raw materials, equipment, human power and information, strategic management, standards and specifications ..., etc), so that all contribute in the quest to achieve the goal of the organization which is concentrated in achieving optimal saturation of the final consumer (Al-bilawi, et al, 2005: 92).

3- Theoretical Framework and Previous Studies

Related to:

3-1: Theoretical Framework:

This section addresses the literature, the intellectual and conceptual quality system of higher education, and academic performance, as follows:

a- The Quality of University Education:

The Quality of University Education is defined as: "Access to efficient curriculum in educational institutions is in its graduates," and contribute to the quality of education in the service of society through improving the input of each of these institutions (Al-warfali, 2011: 87).

And the quality in higher education is the necessary requirements that universities are keen to achieve them for advanced positions within the classification of outstanding universities in the world, and is seeking many of the distinguished universities in the world to apply the standard of the quality management to improve the performance of employees and ensure the quality of its outputs (Hmdto, 2011:112).

Also the quality of university education as an administrative process based on a set of values, and derive energy movement of information, which employs the talents of employees, and invest their intellectual creatively to ensure continuous improvement of the organization, which is a translation of the needs and desires of graduates of the University of the output of the education system in universities to the characteristics and standard specified in the graduate, as a basis for designing programs continuous development (Rhodes, 2005: 37).

In light of the foregoing, the quality of university education was whole philosophy to work in educational institutions, they set the tone administrative practice in order to achieve improvement and development ongoing processes of education and the development of educational outcomes on the basis of collective action to ensure the satisfaction of faculty members, students, parents and the labor market (Al-nasani, 2003: 10).

b - The Elements of the Quality of University Education:

We can summarizing the elements of quality in higher education institutions, including the following (Lamia, et al, 2011: 533):

- 1- There are realistic goals and tasks can be achieved.
- 2- Policies, systems and mechanisms for the implementation of access to the targets.
- 3- The presence of binding standards in the field of academic and administrative area and student area and the area structure and resources.

4- A reference to clarify the determinants of the nature and quality of academic programs and degrees in various disciplines and measuring them.

5- Measurement systems and performance indicators specific and sophisticated to judge the policies, systems and mechanisms for implementation in the framework of the objectives and tasks.

6- Existence of an institutionalized system of continuous quality management and assurance aims to audit, accounting and development.

c - The Quality of Academic Performance:

The improvement of academic performance in higher education institutions, involves the desire to lay the foundations of development and modernization, and providing elements of creativity and excellence in a world of accelerating the products of the human mind. The continuation for the performance of institutions of higher education in recent finds there is deterioration in the quality of services provided by these institutions, and perhaps confirms this decline is the decline in test scores and deficiencies in the basic skills of graduates and the increasing dropout rates for students.

All this confirms the need to search for new treatments that can help higher education institutions to promote and address the deterioration of those (Madani, 2011:1085).

It is no doubt that the need to enhance the performance of academic merit, then a pause of a nature to cause the change in university education and improving the quality of academic performance, through the adoption of mechanisms to improve the performance of university and renovated, among them the following (Sunil, 2006: 35), (Peter, 2007:21):

- 1- To renew the philosophical framework for the university administration.
- 2- Innovation in higher education goals and the pattern of the educational process.
- 3- Renewal in the roles required of a faculty members at the university.
- 4- Oriented focus of scientific research.
- 5- To renew the relationship with the university student and changing roles.

3-2: Previous Studies Related to:

Because the importance of the study subject, the researcher saw to need shed light on the set of related studies, among them the following:

- Study (Al-kubaisi, 2011): "The fact of the quality of university teaching and ways to improve it".

The study aimed to assess the reality of the quality of teaching and ways to improve it from the perspective of faculty members at the Anbar University. The researcher used the questionnaire as a research tool included four areas included on the (64) items, were then test the sincerity of the tool and its reliability, after that the tool applied on the study sample (61) faculty member. The study came to the conclusion: There exist a decline in the quality of university teaching, and the reason for this decline attributed to some faculty members in disciplines not received adequate educational preparation in the light of a culture of quality.

- Study (Al-subaie, 2010): "The fact of teaching skills to faculty members of the Faculty of Applied Science in the light of the comprehensive quality standards from the perspective of students of Umm Al-Qura University."

The study aimed to identify the reality of teaching skills to faculty members and the degree of engaging these skills in the teaching of science in light of the comprehensive quality standards, the researcher used for this purpose questionnaire included four areas (science teaching skills in the light of the total quality standards), and included on the (73) teaching skill. were then test the sincerity of the tool and its reliability, after that the tool applied on the study sample (189) students. Was reached some conclusions, including:

a- low level of performance of teaching staff in departments of science teaching skills, the level of overall quality .

b-There are exist statistically significant differences in the degree of exercise the teaching staff of science teaching skills, and all were in favor of teaching staff in the Biology Department.

- Study (Venkatraman, 2007): "A framework for Implementing TQM in Higher Education Programs" .

The study aimed to provide a framework for total quality management that focuses on continuous improvements in education, as an appropriate means to implement the requirements of total quality management in higher education. Were analyzed total quality management programs in education by looking at various factors (such as existing educational practices, and constraints of total quality management, and return on investment) in the applying the total quality management in education. The study concluded that these discoveries led to the development of a

framework of TQM depends on (Deming wheel) to implement continuous improvements in higher education.

- Study (Ahmed & Hamdoon, 2007): "The Challenges and Obstacles of TQM Implementation in the Higher Education Institutions: The case Sharjah".

The study aimed to identify the challenges and obstacles facing in applying the total quality management in higher education in the UAE. The study was conducted at the University of Sharjah., The findings suggest that all the obstacles set out in the instrument of the study (questionnaire), it considered as a real obstacles facing workers in University, which is already preventing the implementation of total quality management system correctly and successful at the University of Sharjah. On the other hand, the results showed that there is a semi-consensus views of the university employees about the importance of adapting to the quality system in education.

- Study (Gavriel & Edward, 2006): "The Difficulty in Implementation TQM in the Higher Education of Institutions / Student Roles" .

The study aimed to identify how to implement total quality management in higher education, through the identification and analysis of dual roles for students and teachers. The survey also looked at the shortcomings in applying the requirements of the total quality management in higher education, as well as evaluating the concept of dual roles for students and measures their impact on the strengthening of the educational process through the interaction between these roles. Have contributed to the study in understanding the roles of the student / teacher and how to apply the total quality in higher education as better, and has provided a new method to enhance the evaluation process as a measure the quality of education.

- Study (Al-uraimi, 2005): "Estimating the degree of academic accreditation standards for colleges of education in the Sultanate Oman as envisaged by administrative leaders and academics".

The study aimed to identify the estimate the applying degree of academic accreditation standards for

colleges of education in the Sultanate Oman from the standpoint of administrative leaders and academics, and determine the differences in their estimates of the degree of standards accreditation attributed to some personality variables (sex, job, qualification, experience years, and college). Was built questionnaire consisted of six areas included on the (100) item, were distributed among the six areas. Been confirmed the sincerity of the tool and it's reliability, after that was applied on the study sample of (109) administrative and academic staff in colleges of education. The study found that there are statistically significant differences between the means estimates of the study sample attributed to (sex), in favor of the (males), and (qualification), in favor of the (doctorates).

4- Methods and Procedures:

4-1: Study Approach:

In the light of the nature of the problem of the study and its objectives, the researcher adopted a descriptive approach to describe the study sample responses and their estimates about the applying degree of the quality standards of university education, as well as evaluate them to describe the level of the quality of academic performance in Jordanian universities. On the other hand, the study used the analytical approach to measure the differences between the means responses of respondents about the applying degree of the quality standards of university education attributed to some personality variables, as well as to measure the differences between the means responses of respondents about the level of their assessment of the quality of academic performance in Jordanian universities according to some personality variables.

4-2: Study population and its Sample:

A - Study Population:

The study population consists of all faculty members whom are working in Zarqa university, and numbered (253) faculty member does not include part-time lecturers.

B - Study Sample:

The study sample consists of (127) faculty member, selected according to stratified random sample method, by (50%) from the population size and each layer of the classes. As shown in Table No.(1) the following:

Table (1): The Study Population and the Number of Distributed Questionnaires

Job Title	Population	Sample	Questionnaires Distributed	Recovered Questionnaires	Valid Questionnaires
Dean	9	5	5	5	5
Dean Assistant	12	6	6	6	6
President Department	27	14	14	13	13
Members	205	102	102	96	92
Total	253	127	127	120	116

Source: Zarqa University / Department of Human Resources / 2013.

Then the researcher distributed (127) questionnaire at members of the sample, were recovered (120) questionnaire, where the percentage of questionnaires recovered is (94.5%), and after review and audit questionnaires recovered, were excluded (4) questionnaires for not expire because of lack of accuracy of the information contained in each , and failure to respond to a number of items in others, and thus the number of valid questionnaires for statistical analysis (116) questionnaire, and the percentage of the number of valid questionnaires with respect to recovered is (96.7%).

After you have determined the final sample for the study of (116) member, were distributed to members of the study sample by personality variables. And the Table No.(2) illustrates this:

Table (2): Describe the characteristics of the study sample in Zarqa University

No.	Variables	Specialty	Frequency	Percentage %
1	Gender	Male	100	86.2
		Female	16	13.8
2	Job Title	Dean	5	4.3
		Dean Assistant	6	5.2
		President Department	13	11.2
		Members	92	79.3
3	Qualification	Master	17	14.7
		PhD.	99	85.3
4	Academic Rank	Teacher	17	14.7
		Assistant Prof.	74	63.8
		Associate Prof.	21	18.1
		Professor	4	3.4
5	Experience Years in University	Less than 4	39	33.6
		4 - 8	41	35.3
		8 - 12	22	19.0
		12 and more	14	12.1

4-3: Study Tool:

In order to achieve the objectives of the study, and after returning to the literature on educational and administrative standards of applying the quality of university education, the researcher built a tool to measure the extent of the applying and its impact on enhancing the academic performance quality in Jordanian universities. The tool consisted three parts, the first part included the personality variables of (gender, job title, qualification, academic rank, and experience years in the university), while the second part dealt with the quality standards of university education, and included (35) items, distributed on the seven standards for the educational quality by (5) items of each standard, while the third part dealt with the variable of academic performance quality and consists of (10) items. Has been used Likert Scale, to measure the applying degree of the educational quality standards, and the evaluation level of the academic performance quality. Was the adoption of a measure of the quality standards of university education, and the academic performance quality is divided into three levels, where it calculated by dividing the difference between the highest value (5) and the lowest value (1) at three levels, that is mean, the cut-off grade is $\{(1-5 / 3 = 1.33\}$. Thus, the three levels as follows:

- Low applying degree (1-2.33).
- Medium applying degree (2.34-3.67)
- High applying degree (2.68-5)

After that was measured the tool sincerity and its reliability, as follows:

A- Tool Sincerity:

Has been verified honesty virtual (Face Validity) of the study tool, through display on a group of experts and arbitrators with expertise and knowledge programs of total quality in education and educational administration at Zarqa University and Jordanian universities, and the goal of arbitration examining the extent of appropriate formulation of items linguistically, and the extent of items belonging to the variables of the study. Has been taking into account the observations of experts and arbitrators, as been reworded some items and delete the others from them. In addition standard seventh to the standards of the quality of university education, is designed so that the questionnaire is designed in its final form.

B - Tool Reliability:

To check the stability of the questionnaire, the researcher using the method (Test-retest), were distributed questionnaire to a sample of (20) teaching staff from outside the sample of the original study sample have been applied by the tool of the study, and the difference of two weeks between the two tests, and by reliability coefficient of stability according to correlation coefficient (Spearman), where the coefficient stability overall tool is (0.96). The reliability coefficient was calculated for the tool (internal consistency of the questionnaire items) using (Cronbach Alpha) coefficient, and the reliability coefficient for the overall tool is (0.95), as shown in Table No.(3) the following:

Table (3): Results of Reliability (Internal Consistency of the Questionnaire items)

Variables	No. of items	Test - retest	Cronbach Alpha
Educational Quality	5	0.90	0.89
Administrative Leadership Quality	5	0.81	0.77
Quality Culture	5	0.71	0.68
Focus on Beneficiaries	5	0.76	0.75
Employees in the University	5	0.86	0.84
Improvement and Development	5	0.87	0.87
Service Quality of Students and Community	5	0.93	0.92
Academic Performance Quality	10	0.92	0.91
Overall Tool	45	0.96	0.95

4-4: Methods of Statistical Treatment:

After completion of the discharge resolution data in the computer, were used some Statistical descriptive and analytical methods, which its available in the Statistical package of Social Sciences (SPSS), in order to answer the study questions and test the hypotheses, and the Statistical methods that were used for the purposes of statistical analysis of the data are:

- 1- Coefficient of Cronbach alpha.
- 2- Correlation Coefficient (Spearman).
- 3- Frequencies and Percentages.
- 4- Means and Standard Deviations.
- 5- One-Sample Kolmogorov – Smirnov Test.
- 6- Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) Test.
- 7- One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA).
- 8- Scheffe's Test.

5- Statistical Analysis of the Data:

The purpose of this section to present the results of statistical analysis of data subjects' responses of the study, which was reached through the use of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

Before answering the study questions and the hypotheses test, should be verified from the distribution of the data, and is the data distributed (Normal Distribution) or not? By test the following statistical hypothesis:

H₀: A questionnaire data is distributed normal distribution.

H₁: A questionnaire data is not distributed normal distribution.

To test the previous hypothesis was used (One-Sample Kolmogorov - Smirnov Test), as shown in Table No.(4) the following:

Table (4): Results of One-Sample Kolmogorov - Smirnov Test

Variables	No. of Observations	Calculated (Z)	P-value
Educational Quality	116	1.362	0.089
Administrative Leadership Quality	116	1.083	0.192
Quality Culture	116	1.578	0.057
Focus on Beneficiaries	116	1.130	0.156
Employees in the University	116	1.119	0.163
Improvement and Development	116	1.244	0.091
Service Quality of Students and Community	116	1.264	0.082
Academic Performance Quality	116	0.966	0.308

Critical value of (Z) is (1.96) at the level ($\alpha = 0.05$).

The final results in Table No.(4),explained the calculated values of (Z) for all variables are less than the critical value of (Z) (1.96), as well as that all (P-values) are greater than the level ($\alpha = 0.05$). In the light of previous results will be not to reject the null hypothesis (H₀), which states that {A questionnaire data is distributed normal distribution}.

On the other hand, the researcher used the (VIF) test, to test the Multicollinearity between the independent variables (quality standards of university education). And the Table No.(5) shows the results as follows:

Table (5): The results of (Variance Inflation Factors-VIF) Test

Independent Variables	VIF	Tolerance
Educational Quality	1.585	0.631
Administrative Leadership Quality	3.312	0.302
Quality Culture	2.176	0.460
Focus on Beneficiaries	2.863	0.349
Employees in the University	2.009	0.498
Improvement and Development	1.962	0.510

Service Quality of Students and Community

1.380

0.724

Critical value of (VIF) is equal to (5).

The results in Table No.(5), explained that there is no Multicollinearity between quality standards of university education which are (Educational Quality, Administrative leadership Quality, Quality Culture, Focus on Beneficiaries, Employees in the University, Improvement and Development, and Service Quality of Students and Community), which are confirmed by the calculated values of (VIF) test, and all these values are less than the critical value of (VIF) test which is equal to (5).

After it was certain that the distribution of the data is (Normal Distribution), and there is no (Multicollinearity) between (quality standards of university education), it has become possible to make all the descriptive statistics (means, and standard deviations), and test the statistical hypothesis (correlation analysis and measure the differences).

To facilitate the display the study results, were classified according to the sequence of questions and the hypothesis contained therein, as follows:

5-1: The results related to the first question:

What is the applying degree of the educational quality standards in Zarqa University from the view point of the study sample?

To answer the first question of the study, it has been calculated the means and standard deviations to assess the study sample on each of the quality standards of university education.

The results in table No.(6), refers to the responses analysis of the sample study about applying degree of the quality standards of university education in Zarqa University. The table includes the means for all standards in order to determine the intensity level to answer about each standard, and the standard deviations for the purpose of diagnosis the dispersion of answers about means.

Table (6): Means and Standard Deviations for the Educational Quality Standards

No.	The Standards	Mean	Std. Deviation	Rank	Applying Degree
1	Educational Quality	3.96	0.78	1	High
2	Administrative Leadership Quality	3.58	0.66	5	Medium
3	Quality Culture	3.66	0.57	2	Medium
4	Focus on Beneficiaries	3.62	0.63	3	Medium
5	Employees in the University	3.59	0.76	4	Medium
6	Improvement and Development	3.57	0.74	6	Medium
7	Service Quality of Students and Community	3.54	0.89	7	Medium
-	Educational Quality Standards	3.65	0.51	-	Medium

The results in Table No.(6), refers to inclination the means of the educational quality standards to rise from the view point of the sample study in Zarqa university, with means (3.96, 3.58, 3.66, 3.62, 3.59, 3.57, 3.54) respectively, and all means larger than the test criteria (3) of (5) on (Likert Scale). These results indicate to the possession of teaching staff a clear vision about the importance of each standard of the educational quality standards, which indicates that the evaluation of the study sample for the applying degree of the educational quality standards in Zarqa University was a (positive), and this means that the Zarqa University apply the degree of the standards mentioned are (medium), from the view point of the study sample in the mentioned university.

5-2: The results related to the second question:

What is the evaluation level of the academic performance quality at Zarqa University from the view point of the study sample?

To answer the second question of the study, it has been calculated the means and standard deviations to assess the study sample for each item of the academic performance quality.

The results in Table No.(7), refer to the responses analysis of the sample study about the evaluation level for the items of the academic performance quality in Zarqa University.

Table (7): Means and Standard Deviations for the items of the Academic Performance Quality

No.	The Items	Mean	Std. Deviation	Rank	Evaluation Degree
1	Applying the quality of university education system, works to improve the skill and academic side for teaching staff.	3.76	1.06	10	High
2	The university administration's interest in applying the academic promotions system in the university, contributes in enhancing the academic performance quality for teaching staff.	4.02	0.96	5	High
3	To encourage and support scientific research in the university helps to develop the academic performance quality for teaching staff.	4.28	0.66	1	High
4	Adoption the system of incentive and rewards in the university, contributes in enhancing the academic performance quality for teaching staff.	4.06	0.97	3	High
5	Applying the quality of university education system, contributes to develop of curricula for various faculties and disciplines.	3.98	0.91	6	High
6	The efficient participation of teaching staff in decision making process in the university enhances the academic performance quality for teaching staff.	3.96	0.96	7	High
7	The university administration's interest in the psychological and social aspects for teaching staff enhances the academic performance quality for him.	3.91	0.92	8	High
8	To support the university for teaching staff sworn affidavits system, to attend conferences abroad, contributes in enhance the academic performance quality for their.	4.23	0.89	2	High
9	The university administration's interest in training the teaching staff and raising the level of their efficiency, enhances the academic performance quality for their.	4.05	1.03	4	High
10	To relieves the control constraints on teaching staff in the university, contributes in enhance the academic performance quality for their.	3.90	1.10	9	High
-	Academic Performance Quality	4.02	0.71	-	High

The results in Table No.(7), refers to increase the mean of academic performance quality variable, where the mean (4.02) which is larger than the test criteria (3) of (5) on (Likert Scale), with standard deviation (0.71). This finding suggests the possession of the study sample members a clear vision about the variable of academic performance quality and every item of it's items, which indicates that the evaluation about the (academic performance quality) by teaching staff in Zarqa University was a (positive), and this means that the evaluation degree of performance in mentioned university is (high), from the view point.

And with respect to each item of (academic performance quality), the results indicate that the item number (3) which states: (To encourage and support scientific research in the university helps to develop the academic performance quality for teaching staff), you may come in (1st rank) on the ladder of priorities for evaluation of teaching staff in Zarqa University, with mean (4.28), and standard deviation (0.66). While the item number (1) that states: (Applying the quality of university education system, works to improve the skill and academic side for teaching staff), came in (10th rank) on the ladder of priorities for evaluation of teaching staff in the university, with mean (3.76), and standard

deviation (1.06). This means that the university mentioned that the degree of the perform services academic is (high), from the perspective of teaching staff.

5-3: The results related to the test of Hypotheses:

Will test the hypotheses of the study related to the correlations and measuring the differences, by using the correlation coefficient (Spearman), and the Analysis of Variance, respectively. The following is a detailed explanation of the results of hypothesis testing, as follows:

a- Test the first hypothesis:

H₀₁: There is no statistically significant relationship at the level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), between the academic performance quality and each standard of the quality standards of the university education.

To test the previous hypothesis, was used the correlation coefficient (Spearman), as shown in Table No.(8) the following:

Table (8): Correlation coefficients (Spearman) between the academic performance quality and each one of the educational quality standards

Variables	Education al Quality	Administrativ e Leadership Quality	Quality Culture	Focus on Beneficiaries	Employees in the University	Improveme nt and Developmen t	Service Quality of Students and Community
Academic Performan ce Quality	0.449 **	0.282 **	0.211*	0.411**	0.583 **	0.293 **	0.471**
P-value	0.000	0.002	0.023	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000

The results in Table No.(8), explained that there exist a positive correlation and statistically significant at the level ($\alpha = 0.05$), between the academic performance quality and each one of the educational quality standards. Which is supported by the calculated (P-values) for correlation coefficients, and all values are less than the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$). This means that will be reject the null hypothesis (H_{01}).

b- Test the second hypothesis:

H₀₂: There are no statistically significant differences at the level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), between the means responses of the study sample about the applying degree of the educational quality standards in Zarqa University from the view point.

To test the previous hypothesis, was used the analysis of variance (ANOVA), as shown in Table No.(9) the following:

Table (9): Analysis of variance (ANOVA), to test the differences between the means responses of the study sample about the applying degree of the educational quality standards

Source of Variations	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2.047	6	0.341	0.751	0.693
Within Groups	365.713	805	0.454		
Total	367.760	811	-		

{Critical value of (F) test with degrees of freedom of the numerator and denominator (6, 805), at the level ($\alpha = 0.05$)} = 2.10

The results in Table No.(9), refers to the calculated value of (F) (0.751), which is less than of the critical value (F) (2.10), and the statistical significance (Sig.) (0.693) is greater than the level ($\alpha = 0.05$). This means that, will be not reject the null hypothesis (H_{02}), and this means, there are no statistically significant differences at the level ($\alpha = 0.05$), between the means responses of the study sample about the applying degree of the educational quality standards in Zarqa University from the view point.

c- Test the third hypothesis:

H₀₃: There are no statistically significant differences at the level of moral ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), between the mean responses of the study sample about the applying degree of the educational quality standards, attributed to some personality variables (job title, qualification, academic rank, and experience years in the university).

To test the previous hypothesis was used the analysis of variance (ANOVA), as shown in Table No.(10) the following:

Table (10): Analysis of variance (ANOVA), to test the differences between the means responses of the study sample about the applying degree of the educational quality standards, attributed to the personality variables

Personality Variables	Source of Variations	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Job Title	Between Groups	0.641	3	0.214	0.836	0.482
	Within Groups	28.976	112	0.256		
Qualification	Between Groups	0.030	1	0.030	0.115	0.735
	Within Groups	29.587	114	0.260		
Academic Rank	Between Groups	1.127	3	0.376	1.480	0.225
	Within Groups	28.490	112	0.254		
Experience Years	Between Groups	5.621	3	1.874	8.757	0.000
	Within Groups	23.996	112	0.214		

The results in Table No.(10), indicates to:

1- There are no statistically significant differences at the level ($\alpha = 0.05$), between the means responses of the study sample about the applying degree of the educational quality standards, attributed to the personality variables (job title, qualification, and academic rank). Which are supported by the calculated values of (F) for the mentioned variables, with values equals to (0.836, 0.115, 1.480) respectively, as well as the values of statistical significance (Sig.) (0.482, 0.735, 0.225), all greater than the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$). This means that will be not rejecting the null hypothesis (H₀₃).

2- There exist statistically significant differences at the level ($\alpha = 0.05$), between the means responses of the study sample about the applying degree of the educational quality standards, attributed to the personality variable (experience years in the university) only. Which is supported by the calculated value of (F) (8.757), as well as the value of (P-value) is less than the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$). This means that will be reject sub of the null hypothesis (H₀₃).

After the verification of the existence of statistically significant differences between the means responses of the study sample about the applying degree of the educational quality standards attributed to the personality variable (experience years at the university) only, should now find, in favor of these differences between the means are attributed, the researcher used for this purpose (Scheffe's) test. And the Table No.(11) below, shows the test results, showed (Scheffe's) test for a posteriori comparisons between means attributed to the personality variable (experience years in the university):

Table (11): The results of (Scheffe's) test for a posteriori comparisons between the means, attributed to the personality variable (experience years in the university)

Experience Years	Means	Less than 4 Years	4 - 8	8 - 12	12 Year and more
Less than 4 Years	3.36	-	046*	0.52*	0.19
4 - 8	3.82		-	0.06	0.27*
8 - 12	3.88			-	0.32*
12 Year and more	3.55				-

- The differences between the means represent absolute values.

The results in Table No.(11), showed the (Scheffe's) test for a posteriori comparisons between the means responses of the study sample about the applying degree of the educational quality standards, attributed to (experience years in the university), and most of the differences are statistically significant at the level ($\alpha = 0.05$). This means that will be reject sub of the null hypothesis (H_{03}), and these means there are statistically significant differences at the level ($\alpha = 0.05$), between the means responses of the study sample about the applying degree of the educational quality standards, attributed to (experience years in the university) in favor of the study sample whom the experience years lie within the class (8-12) years.

d- Test the fourth hypothesis:

H₀₄: There are no statistically significant differences at the level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), between the means responses of the study sample about the evaluation level of the academic performance quality, attributed to some personality variables (job title, qualification, academic rank, and experience years in the university).

To test the previous hypothesis was used the analysis of variance (ANOVA), as shown in Table No.(12) the following:

Table (12): Analysis of variance (ANOVA), to test the differences between the means responses of the study sample about the evaluation level of the academic performance quality, attributed to the personality variables

Personality Variables	Source of Variations	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Job Title	Between Groups	1.814	3	0.605	1.210	0.309
	Within Groups	55.965	112	0.500		
Qualification	Between Groups	0.012	1	0.012	0.024	0.877
	Within Groups	57.767	114	0.507		
Academic Rank	Between Groups	1.073	3	0.358	0.708	0.550
	Within Groups	56.706	112	0.506		
Experience Years	Between Groups	3.675	3	1.225	2.536	0.060
	Within Groups	54.104	112	0.483		

The results in Table No.(12), explained that there are no statistically significant differences at the level ($\alpha = 0.05$), between the means responses of the study sample about the evaluation level of the academic performance quality, attributed to the personality variables (job title, qualification scientific, academic rank, and experience years in university). Which are supported by the calculated values of (F) for the mentioned variables, with values equals to (1.210, 0.024, 0.708, 2.536) respectively, as well as the values of statistical significance (Sig.) (0.309, 0.877, 0.550, 0.060), all greater than the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$). This means that will be not rejecting the null hypothesis (H_{04}).

6- Discussion the findings and Recommendations:

In this section will be discussion the study results, and includes the most important recommendations of the study in light of the results, as follows:

6-1: The result's Discussion:

a- Discussion the results related to the first question:

The results of the first question, related to the applying degree of the quality standards of university education in Zarqa University, has ranged between (medium and high) from the view point of faculty members. The educational quality standard received at the (first rank) on the ladder of priorities of the study sample, followed by the quality culture standard in the (second rank), while the standards (focus on the beneficiaries, employees at the university, the quality of administrative leadership, improvement and development, and the quality service of student and community) received at the ranks (third, fourth, fifth,

sixth and seventh) respectively. This was attributed to the faculty members in the University have a clear vision on the mechanism of the applying the quality standards of university education in Zarqa University. The ranking of these standards as such, as a result of higher perception of faculty members about the importance of the standards on the ladder of priorities in enhancing the academic performance quality in the mentioned university .

The results regarding with the applying degree of the quality standards of university education in Zarqa University, agreement with the study results of Gavriel & Edawrd (2006), and the study of Ahmed & Hamdoon (2007). And the results of this study differ from the study results of Al-subaie (2010), and the study of Al-kubaisi (2011).

b- Discussion the results related to the second question:

The results showed on the second question, that the evaluation of faculty members in Zarqa University to the academic performance quality and for every item for this variable, was (high) from the view point. This demonstrates that the faculty members are fully convinced about the effective role of the quality standards of university education in Zarqa University applied to support and enhance the academic performance quality in university.

And to the knowledge of the researcher, there are no studies that the results are agreement or different with the results of this study.

c- Discussion the results of the first hypothesis:

The results of testing the first hypothesis, refers to the existence of a positive correlation and statistically significant at the level ($\alpha = 0.05$), between the academic performance quality and with each one of the quality standards of university education. This means, that the increasing interest of Zarqa University for the quality standards of university education will contribute significantly in enhancing and improving the academic performance quality in the mentioned university. In light of the above, the mentioned standards will have a significant impact in enhancing the academic performance quality in Zarqa University.

And to the knowledge of the researcher, there are no studies that the results are agreement or different with the results of this study.

d- Discussion the results of the second hypothesis:

The results of testing the second hypothesis, explained that there are no existence statistically significant differences at the level ($\alpha = 0.05$), between the means responses of faculty members about the applying degree of the educational quality standards in Zarqa University from the view point. This means that the faculty members in the university have a culture on the applying the mentioned standards, and that these standards have the same interest on the ladder of priorities, without discrimination between the standards, because the impact of these standards in enhance the academic performance quality in the university.

And to the knowledge of the researcher, there are no studies that the results are agreement or different with the results of this study.

e- Discussion the results of the third hypothesis:

The results of testing the third hypothesis, refers to the existence of statistically significant differences at the level ($\alpha = 0.05$), between the means responses of faculty members about the applying degree of the educational quality standards in Zarqa University, attributed to (experience years in the university), in favor of the faculty members whom the experience in Zarqa university lie within the class (8-12) years.

While not confirmed the existence of statistically significant differences between the means responses of faculty members about the applying degree the educational quality standards in the mentioned university, attributed to (job title, qualification, and academic rank).

And to the knowledge of the researcher, there are no studies agreements with the results of this study. While the results of this study differ with the study results of Al-uraimi (2005) .

f- Discuss the results of the fourth hypothesis:

The results of testing the fourth hypothesis, explained that there are no existence statistically significant differences at the level ($\alpha = 0.05$), between the means responses of faculty members about the evaluation level for the academic performance quality in Zarqa University, attributed to (Job title, qualification, academic rank, and experience years in the university).

And to the knowledge of the researcher, there are no studies that the results are agreement or different with the results of this study.

6-2: Recommendations:

In light of the results, the study recommended the following:

a- To raise and deepen the awareness of all employees in the university, for the quality culture and importance in the development of the concepts of Total Quality in higher education, in order to enhance the academic performance quality in Jordanian universities, and through holding seminars specialized and workshops on a regular basis, is of which illustrate the importance of the quality culture and it's role in enhancing the academic performance quality.

b- Necessarily to send the faculty members in Jordanian universities, to training courses outside the country, to know and learn about the experiences of the world about the quality of higher education, in order to gain the experience and knowledge, and the development of teaching skills so as to enhance the quality of their academic performance.

c- The study suggest to doing the researches and comparative studies between institutions of higher education, which applying the educational quality standards, among other identical institutions did not apply the quality system, to identify differences in outputs, and treat the weaknesses that are believed to hinder the process of applying quality standards.

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